

Estimation of precipitation and moisture budget spatiotemporal variability using reanalysis and the ground truth data over upper Blue Nile basin in Ethiopia

PhD Thesis Presentation

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December 2019

Outline

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1. Introduction

■ The formation of precipitation (P)

When the north pole tilts toward the sun, it gets more radiation - more warmth during the summer

SUMMER (Northern Hemisphere)

North Pole

When the north pole tilts toward the sun, the south pole tilts away
So when it's summer in the north,
it's winter in the south

WINTER (Southern Hemisphere)

Intense radiation at the equator warms the air

Air cools as it rises, moisture condenses and falls as rain

Warm air rises, collecting moisture

Lots of rain in the tropics! (**Local moisture contribution**)

Motivations and Statement of the problem

- Accurate estimation of P is challenging and demanding (Deepak et al., 2013), especially over UBNB is not satisfactory, because
 - ✓ UBNB has consists of variable topographic area (Abera et al., 2017)
 - ✓ P didn't have linear nature (Deepak et al., 2013)
 - ✓ Lack of sufficient hydrometeorological stations (Mariam et al., 2016; Abera et al., 2017)
 - ✓ Lake of remote measurements (radar) and reformulated the model (Z-R relation)
 - ✓ There is no study conducted to consider effects of local MB and middle atmosphere for P variability

Statement of the problem and related works

- Radar Z-R relation model and its errors were studied by (Emad et al. 2008; AghaKouchak et al., 2010; Andrea, 2015).
- However, they have not been verified on the projectile rainfall motion errors.
- **MB and P variability** were studied by different authors in different countries.
- For e.g. at China by Zengxin et al. (2009), over Mediterranean by Fengjun et al. (2011); over Amazon Basin by Drumond et al. (2014) and in Africa by Catherine et al. (2014)

Statement of the problem cont...

- In Ethiopia, large scale MB dynamics was studied by the number of authors (**Korecha and Barnston, 2007; Ellen and Asgeir, 2013**)
- But they didn't estimate the contribution of **the study area MB for the P system and its variability.**
- P is also varied from the normal conditions due to the **interaction between middle and lower atmosphere parameters** (**AttaullahKhan and ShuanggenJin, 2016**)
- But, there was no study conduct to this effect **the P variability** in the context of Ethiopia
- **To fill in these gaps, this thesis contains different objectives**

Objectives

- ❖ **Main objective:** Estimation of precipitation and moisture budget spatiotemporal variability over upper Blue Nile basin
- ❖ **Specific objectives**
 - To estimate precipitation intensity from first observation weather radar reflectivity data over upper Blue Nile basin
 - Error modeling radar rainfall estimation through incorporating rain gauge data over upper Blue Nile basin
 - Assessing the performance of reanalysis precipitation products through comparing with the ground truth
 - Estimating the role of upper Blue Nile basin moisture budget and recycling ratio in spatiotemporal precipitation distribution
 - To investigate the precipitation variability by considering effect of middle atmosphere parameters on lower atmosphere

2. Site Description, Measurement techniques, Data Sources, and Methodology

The study area information:

Location: Between 7.40° to 12.5° N and from 34.25° to 39.49° E

Drainage area : 176, 000 km²

Elevation: ranging from 500 m to 4160 m

Economic: mainly agriculture

Climate: Tropical

Mean annual P: ranges from 1040 to 1600 mm (Conway, 2000; Megbar et al., 2019)

Fig. 1. Location map of Upper Blue Nile basin, Ethiopia

Measurement techniques

Parameters	Values
Band	C
Transmitter	Magnetron
Frequency	5.5-5.7 GHz
Peak power	250 kW
Average power	300 W
Pulse Repetition Frequency (PRF)	600 Hz
Antenna diameter	4.5 meter
Gain	45 dB
Polarization	Dual (vertical and horizontal)
Maximum scan rate	40 degree/second

Fig.2. Gauge, satellite, and radar (specification) measurement techniques

Data Sources

Table 1. Different data sources, spatiotemporal resolution, time coverage and corresponding websites are listed below

Data types	Period	Time resolution	Space resolution	Website
Radar	22, Jun-14, Jul 2016	daily	continuous	non
Gauge	1980-2017	daily	34 station per UBNB	non
CRU	1979-2017	monthly	0.5X0.5 degree	http://www.cru.uea.ac.uk
CMAP	1979-2017	monthly	2.5X2.5 degree	www.precip.mon.mean.nc
OLR	1974-2016	monthly	1.0X1.0 degree	www.olr.mon.NOMA.nc
NOAA	1981-2016	monthly	1.0X1.0 degree	www.esrl.noaa.gov/gl_data
CHIRPS	1981-2017	daily	0.05X0.05 degree	www.CHIRPS-2.0/global_daily
ECMWF	1979-2017	daily	0.125X0.125 degree	www.ecmwfdataset

▪ Suggested literatures CRU by [Mitchell and Jones \(2005\)](#), OLR by [Tobin et al. \(2006\)](#) , NOAA by [Richenda et al. \(2004\)](#), CHIRPS by [Funk et al. \(2015\)](#) , and ECMWF by [\(Dee et al., 2011\)](#)

Methods

➤ In situ data have **various missing value**, to fill this missing data, we following equation 1 to equation 4 (**Diro et al., 2008**)

$$C = Y^T Y \quad (1)$$

$$X = (C^T C)^{-1} C Y \quad (2)$$

$$C^{new} = Y X^T (X X^T)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$Y = C^{new} X \quad (4)$$

Validation and projectile motion error correction

- We were applied **different error metrics (bias ratio, MRE, RMSE, and R)** to check the performance of reanalysis data with in-situ data
- **Z-R relation radar model projectile motion error correction**

Fig. 3. The trajectory path of rainfall

Proportional and random error correction

$$Z = aR^b \Rightarrow R = (Z / a)^{1/b} \quad (6)$$

$$R = (Z / a)^{1/b} + (Z / a)^{1/b} \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 \quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon = (Z / a)^{1/b} \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 = R_i - (Z_i / a)^{1/b} \quad (8)$$

The moisture transport flux divergence (MFD) and recycling ratio are given by

$$E - P = MFD = \frac{OF}{A} - \frac{IF}{A} = HA + HD \quad (9)$$

$$R = \frac{E}{E + \frac{IF}{A}} \approx \frac{E}{P + E} \quad (10)$$

❖ Software
➤ MATLAB
➤ CDO
➤ IRIS

3. Results and Discussion

❖ Z-R relation modeling parameter values

Before the application
of projectile motion
error correction

a=50
b=0.89
p.error = 0.30
r.error = -0.08

After the application of
projectile motion error
correction

a=55
b=1.12
p.error = 0.08
r.error = 0.07

$Z=55R^{1.12}$ for **Ethiopia**

$Z=238R^{1.5}$ for **Netherland** (Remko, 2001)

$Z=31R^{1.9}$ for **Brazil** (Nzeukou et al., 2002)

$Z = 116 R^{1.87}$ for **Libya** (Kamil and Medhat, 2009)

$Z=250R^{1.2}$ for **Guyana** (Komalchand and Dhiram, 2016)

Z-R model errors before and after projectile motion

Fig.4. Comparisons of radar and gauge rainfall observation at Dangla and Gonder stations from June 22 to July 14, 2016.

Z-R relation model errors cont...

Fig.5. Proportion error, random error and the total error verses rain gauge measurements

Z-R relation model errors cont...

- The weather radar errors were studied by (Emad et al., 2008 and AghaKouchak et al., 2010) and they found that
 - ✓ The range of **proportional error** varied from -5.70 to 5.90 mm,
 - ✓ Random error varied from -2.50 to 2.00 mm and
 - ✓ The **total error** varied from -5.70 to 5.90 mm.
- Hence, our study error results before the application of projectile motion correction was **nearly similar with previous reports while after projectile correction the total error was reduced by 12%**

Comparisons Between Reanalysis and Gauge data

Fig.6. Long term (1980-2017) daily mean of monthly and annual P in millimeter per day

Comparisons Between Reanalysis and Gauge data cont...

Table 2. The error metrics between reanalysis and gauge P data (1980-2017)

Gauge	Bias ratio	MRE	RMSE	R
ECMWF	0.98	-0.01	0.71	0.82
CHIRPS	1.11	0.10	3.82	0.76
CRU	1.01	0.02	0.23	0.37
CMAP	0.92	-0.18	2.81	0.16

Comparisons of Z-R and ECMWF model

Fig.7. Comparisons between Z-R relation model weather radar P data (left panel) and ECMWF model P data

Comparisons of Z-R and ECMWF model cont...

- The comparison of CHIRPS and ECMWF P with the gauge was studied by **Sahalu et al. (2017); Ayehu et al. (2018); Dinku et al. (2018)**.
- In this study we compared ECMWF data with gauge and radar Z-R relation model **is well agreed and strongly supported the previous findings**
- **Therefore, ECMWF is quite useful to study MB and P variability over the study domain.**

Moisture budget analysis and Recycling ratio

Fig. 8. Spring P, E, E-P and OLR distribution from 1990 to 2017.

Moisture budget analysis and Recycling ratio cont...

Fig. 9. Summer P, E, E-P and OLR distribution from 1990 to 2017

Moisture budget analysis and Recycling ratio cont...

Table 3. The **seasonal and annual P** & evaporation (E) numerical values

Parameter	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Annual
P (mm)	146.00	551.50	2007.45	1460.10	1045.10
E (mm)	175.20	189.52	200.75	182.50	189.24

- In this thesis, we investigated **ECMWF precipitation data**, the annual average value was 1045.10 mm.
- Similar studies such as **Conway (2000)** using in-situ data that **varied from 1200 to 1600mm**.

Moisture budget analysis and Recycling ratio cont...

Table 4. Seasonal recycling ratio over UPNB from 1979-2017 (eq.18)

Seasons	Percent (%)
December-February (Winter)	35.30
March-May (spring)	19.01
June-August (summer)	09.70
September-November (autumn)	16.33
Annual	20.11

- Recycling ratio over UBNB was far less than [Fengjun et al. \(2011\)](#) finding in which they got 55% but slightly larger than [Jin and Zangvil \(2010\)](#), finding of 18% over the Mediterranean region.
- The minimum area required for MB study which is $1 \times 10^5 \text{ km}^2$ ([Yeh et al., 1998](#)).
- Since our research area is slightly larger than the minimum required for MB study which is $1.76 \times 10^5 \text{ km}^2$.

Moisture budget analysis and Recycling ratio cont...

Fig.10. Graphical abstract of recycling ratio.

Impacts of Middle Atmosphere to Lower Atmosphere

Impacts of Middle Atmosphere to Lower Atmosphere cont...

Fig.12. Spatial variability of P, cloud cover (CC), ISR, O₃, temperature (T) and gravity wave (GW) during the spring season.

Impacts of Middle Atmosphere to Lower Atmosphere cont...

Fig.13. Spatial variability of P, CC, ISR, O₃, T and GW during the summer season.

Impacts of Middle Atmosphere to Lower Atmosphere cont...

- The similar findings to our study indicated that
- **O₃ concentration is increased with T** (Solberg et al., 2008; Jacob and Winner, 2009; JaneCoate et al., 2016).
- T and ISR were affected by CC, O₃ concentration, GW, and greenhouse gases such as CO₂ and CH₄ (Litynsky et al., 2006; Attaullah and Shuanggen, 2016).

Conclusions

- Projectile rainfall motion error correction is **very important to reduced Z-R relation error modeling.**
- By applying the application of projectile motion correction the **total error is reduced by 12%.**
- ECMWF products have **substantially useful to study P and MB variability over UBNB in Ethiopia.**
- The calculated recycling ratios for summer, autumn, spring and winter were **found 9.70%, 16.33%, 19.01%, and 35.30% respectively with annual average value of 20.11%.**
- The annual local evaporated moisture **is less contributed of P over UBNB region.** But its contribution **is around 79% to neighboring countries such as Egypt and Sudan.**
- Annual P is directly **negatively influenced by T, strong GW and ISR.**

Recommendations

- We recommended that, Ethiopia and downstream countries concerned bodies should take **necessary actions to mitigate and renovate the UBNB climate and hydrology.**
- We wish a detailed study on **MB and recycling ratio in context of Ethiopia.**
- Further study is needed to **determine the frequency of strong GW occurrence and its relation to the Ethiopian drought events.**
- Our **decadal trend analysis** indicated that in near **percent time deficiency of precipitation** is observed due to unknown factors, therefore in the future, the study of **atmospheric chemistry will need**

Publications

From this PhD Thesis

1. **Megbar W. Birhan**, U. Jaya Prakasha Raju and Samuel.T. Kenea (2018).
Estimation of rainfall intensity from first observation weather radar reflectivity data over upper Blue Nile Basin, Ethiopia. Transactions on Science and Technology Vol. 5, No. 4, 223 – 232.
2. **Megbar. W. Birhan**, U.Jaya Prakasha Raju and Samuel.T. Kenea (2019).
Estimating the role of upper Blue Nile basin moisture budget and recycling ratio in spatiotemporal precipitation distribution. Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-territorial physics 193 (2019) 105064:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp>.
3. **Megbar Wondie Birhan**, U.Jaya Prakasha Raju and Samuel Takele Kenea (2019)
Estimating the influence of precipitation variability by considering effect of middle atmosphere parameters on lower atmosphere over upper Blue Nile basin in Ethiopia. Modeling Earth Systems and Environment; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-019-00596-w>
4. **Megbar. W. Birhan**, U.Jaya Prakasha Raju, and Samuel.T. Kenea, (2019). Error modeling radar rainfall estimation through incorporating rain gauge data over upper Blue Nile basin, Ethiopia. **International Journal of Computing Science and Applied Mathematics**, vol. 5, no. 2; <http://dx.doi.org/10.12962/j24775401.v5i2.4687>

From related works

1. **Megbar Wondie** and Tadesse Terefe (2016).
Assessment of drought in Ethiopia by using self calibrated Palmer drought severity index (Sc-PDSI). International Journal of Engineering and Management Science, I.J.E.M.S., Vol.7 (2) 2016: 108-117.
2. **Megbar. W. Birhan** and Fentahun. A. Worku (2018).
Impact of climate change and variability in the hydrology of Chokie mountain basin, Ethiopia. International Journal of Engineering and Management Science, I.J.E.M.S., Vol.9 (4) 2018:44-51

Presentations in conferences (16)

Acknowledgments

- ❑ Advisors, U.Jaya Prakasha Raju (PhD) and Samuel Takele (PhD)
- ❑ The earlier and current heads of Physics Department of Bahir Dar University
- ❑ Coordinator of the PhD program, Physics Department of Bahir Dar University
- ❑ Blue Nile Water Institute (Bahir Dar University)
- ❑ Debre Markos University
- ❑ National Meteorological Agency (NMA)
- ❑ All colleagues, staffs and PhD candidates of Physics Department of Bahir Dar University
- ❑ Finally, my deep gratitude goes to my family and my wife for financial support and give moral appreciations.

A pixelated, low-resolution image of the Earth, showing continents and oceans in shades of blue, green, and brown. The globe is centered and occupies most of the frame. Overlaid on the globe is the text "Thank you for your attentions!!!".

Thank you for your attentions!!!